

Paper 7

Study on an Introduction to Halakki Tribes at Uttara Kannada District

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Abstract

*The Halakki Vokkaliga is a group of [vokkaligas](#), predominantly in [Uttara Kannada](#) district of [Karnataka](#), India. Halakki Vokkaligas living in the foot of [Western Ghats](#) are known as the "Aboriginals of Uttara Kannada". Their way of living is still ancient. The women adorn themselves with beads and necklaces, heavy nose rings and distinctive ornaments. Their total population is about [1309](#). The major community residing in this place is [Nador](#). Most people presently residing in Torke are agriculturists. Others indulge in salt production, government jobs, contracting etc. Apart from a sizeable "Halakki-Vokkaliga" community in "Devana", a moderate sized "Harikantra" or fishermen community is also found in Hoskatt. Four population groups, namely, Halakkis, Siddis, Gonds and Havyak Brahmins of Uttara Kannada District of Karnataka state of South India. The term Halavakki is said to be derived from the Kannada term *halu* which means milk and *akki* means rice. Halakki Vakkals, also spelt as Halwakki Vakkal, are a major cultivating community and are confined to the coastal taluks of Uttara Kannada district of Karnataka. The researcher has made attempt to study the Halakki Vokkaliga tribes from Ankola, Uttara Kannada. The main aim is to study is to introduce and identify the challenges of Halakki Vokkaligas. And the objectives are the present practices and the life style of the people and the issues and challenges faced by the Halakki Vokkaligas. The study is exploratory in nature used primary and secondary data as case study.*

Keywords: Halakki Vokkaligas, situation, challenges, cultural, health, social and lifestyle.

1. INTRODUCTION

In this paper the word *tribe* has used as *Community*. Cultural history records and interprets past events involving human beings through the social, cultural, and political milieu of or

relating to the arts and manners that a group favors. Cultural history studies and interprets the record of human societies by denoting the various distinctive ways of living built up by a group of people under consideration. Cultural history involves the aggregate of past cultural activity, such as ceremony, classing practices, and the interaction with locales. Halakki Vokkalu' is a small group in Karnataka and is settled down in four taluks of Uttara Kannada district namely Karwar, Ankola, Kumta and Honnavar. They are thickly populated in and around Ankola and Kumta taluks. Halakki Vokkalu is mild, sober and economically poor people. In Karnataka they are considered as very backward community and placed in the category I group. According to Bhat, the name 'Halakki' probably because, these people are asked to sprinkle milk and rice at the marriage procession of Having Brahmin to prevent evil eye on the newlywed couple. According to the people, acquisition of the name may be due to their occupations like agriculture and dairy work. There is no unanimous opinion regarding the origin of the term.

2. DISTRICT SCENARIO

Uttara Kannada district is one of the biggest districts in the state of Karnataka. It is a beautiful place that has been blessed with abundant natural resources. The district has varied geographical features with thick forest, perennial rivers, abundant flora and fauna and a long coastal line of about 140 Kms in length. Uttara Kannada district is bounded by the Belgaum district and the state of Goa in the North, Dharwar District in the East and by Shimoga and Udupi district in the south. The Halakki Vokkaliga are a [caste](#) group of [vokkaligas](#) of [Karnataka](#), India. They are found predominantly in [Uttara Kannada](#) district. Halakki Vokkaligas living in the foot of [Western Ghats](#) are known as the "Aboriginals of Uttara Kannada". Their way of living is still ancient. The women adorn themselves with beads and necklaces, heavy nose rings and distinctive attire. Halakki Vokkalu are mixed with the other backward communities. Hence, it is very difficult to authentically about their total population. Haalakki Vokkaligas can be seen on both sides of National Highway 17 that passes through Karwar, Ankola, Kumata, Gokarna and Honnavar talluqs of Uttara Kannada district and the parts of land touching the waters of Arabian Sea. There are many ancient societies indicating that there was independent, self-rule. The underlying system of their society is very different. The whole population of the Haalakki tribe has been divided into 7 regions. The religious rituals are bound by these regions. The seven regions are Chandaavara, Gokarna, Kadavaada, Ankola, Nushi Kote, Kumbaara Gadde and Haritte Seemey. A group of Haalakki huts is called 'Koppa'. Many Koppas together form a seemey. Each Koppa has a Gowda and a Budavantha and a Kolkaara to assist him. Leader of the Seemey is called Arasu or Gowda. The power is hereditary. If the judgment pronounced by the Gowda of Koppa is contested, leader of Seemey makes the judgment.

3. ORIGIN OF HAALAKKI VOKKALIGAS

There are no concrete evidences regarding the origins of Haalakki Vokkaligas. However, Dr. R.N. Nayak, who has worked extensively regarding the folk culture of Uttara Kannada, gives the following reasons as to why it can be assumed they originate from Andhra. They are the staunch followers of Thirupathi Thimmappa, Their songs often mention eastern sea and Telugu word ‘haalika’ is very much similar to Halakki. The pronunciation differences in their language such as Na-na, La-la, sa-cha are similar to that in Telugu. The language of Halakki people is Achchagannada. They are the devotees of Thirupathi Thimmappa. Every house compulsorily has a Tulasimane. It is a curious fact as to how these Halakkis, inhabitants of west coast became devotees of eastern Thirupathi Thimmappa. When their traditional rituals and devotional practices are observed, matriarchal culture stands out. Forest plants, animals, hills and brooks are symbols of their clans, which suggests a matriarchal society and that they originated from the forests. Now, they have forgotten the names of their ancient clans. Halakki people recognize a hill of this region as their tribe’s village.

4. SOCIAL ASPECTS

Careful observation shows a marked difference in behaviour, dressing, jewellery, way of looking at life, personality and many other things among Halakki women from one place to the other. Haalakki women of Ankola are jovial talkers. They can happily spill out hundreds of songs in an effortless manner. Only the Haalakki women of Ankola can sing and dance “Thaarley Thaarley” a rain dance. Haalakki women of Honnavara are soft natured. They speak only when it is required. Their songs have a soft quality and are sung in a low-pitched voice. Surprisingly they do not know to dance ‘Thaarley’. Haalakki women of Ankola wear short black beaded necklaces around their neck. Haalakki women of Honnavara wear long yellow, and black beaded necklaces. They wear glass bangles only on the left hand. The kind of brass shoulder bands worn by these women are not seen among the Haalakki women of Ankola. Haalakki women of Ankola wear their sarees short, like a skirt unlike the Haalakki women of Honnavara who wear their sarees long. It looks beautiful when the folds tucked to side of their waists, and they sway while they carry their bundles of firewood on their heads. The reasons for such difference among Haalakki women of Ankola and Honnavara are yet to be found. Their harvest dances too exhibit a lot of regional difference. There are notable differences in the harvest dancing style, costume, songs, singing, literature etc, from region to region. Probably, these races found it difficult to communicate after migrating to different regions because of hills, mountains, rivers and forests. Tribal castes could not mingle with each other since status-based caste restrictions were tighter in the olden days. Hence these differences in behaviour, clothing etc. remained intact. Haalakki of Honnavara interacted with soft natured Havyaka Brahmin women. At the same time, Haalakki women of Ankola interacted with Naadavaru who were basically Kshathriyas. This too might have influenced their personalities and behaviour.

5. CULTURAL ASPECTS

Cultural history related to anthropology and history concern with the cultural traditions and historical experience. It examines the records and narrative descriptions of past matter. Uttara Kannada district is a part of land which has sea corrosion; the coastal area which supports the fact that, Haalakkis came and settled from some other place. In the Suggi songs and Gumte padas of Haalakkis, according to Madevaraya's song, "There was a pariah(holati) woman ruling the seashore lands. This tribe stayed like Thodas of Nilagiri near the foothills and depended on Kumbri system of agriculture. They gradually migrated to riverbanks, seashores, flatlands and started working for landlords. Some own pieces of land after the legislation of 'tiller is the owner'. Then they shifted their occupation and started depending on agriculture for their livelihood. Their connection with the forest and the nature started celebration the harvesting festival related to their occupation agriculture. *Suggi dance*; This dance is particularly on full moon day during the annual harvesting, whole village used to participate in preparing the harvest gear called Suggi kunitha. The whole village used to enjoy during the festival as one family. Even the village head Gowda used to touch the feet of the harvest dancers. This is one of the source of entertainment for whole community.

6. HEALTH ASPECT OF HALAKKI

Medicate them at home by using some techniques of *Patthe* means avoid some food stuffs during illness episode or taking some foods and beverages. After this if the result is *No*, they opt for medicine from the counters ie, *General Shops and Medical Shops (Chemist)*. The observation from field acknowledges the fact that availability of medical shops is comparatively less than any other general shops. If there is no solution for their sickness then they go to the *popular practitioner sector*. Popular practitioner means the lay, non-professional, non specialist domain of the society which is treating for many illnesses since a long back. Halakkis go to these people because they live among and nearby, especially at rural areas where majority of the professional or trained doctors do not prefer to be there and serve in these places. It is purely an issue of availability, accessibility and affordability of a specialist of a treatment. Hence the preference for specialist treatment is at last they try to get out from the illness episode through their prior preferences of treatment gradually shift from one to other. Halakkis sought treatment for their illness from one of the sector mentioned above then they lead routine life. Along this pattern of health seeking they follow one more practice that is magical-religious treatment which goes parallel with other treatments they follow, from [homemade](#) medicine practice to treatment from professional doctors.

CONCLUSION

This is the pattern found among the Halakki Vokkalu tribe's seeking health. This shows that they have their own style of identifying, diagnosing and treating an illness. The parallel system of seeking health is continuing with very strong beliefs and practices, according to a respondent because, it provides a moral and psychological strength and support to both patient and family. By this patient's belief in treatment and medicine get stronger and stronger. Once patient gets enough belief in treatment and medicine his mind starts reacting

positively to the treatment and it results with cure. The respondent's statement denotes that the importance of psychological consideration for any treatment and medicine leads to proper responding from the patients. Wish to conclude this article with all sort of treatments have got their own set of pros and cons, they must work in complimenting to each other instead of any contradictions. Of course it is true that each type of sectors have very different style of diagnosing, treating and following-up the cases but the motto behind those is and must be one that is the betterment of mankind. We don't support any ill practices in the name traditional or [indigenous medicine](#), but the concern is many of illnesses/disease are successfully treated by traditional or indigenous medicine. It has to be recognized and used in public health sector by which more numbers of people get benefited in terms of health and finance.

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